

Atlantic Ecosystems Assessment, Forecasting & Sustainability

Deliverable number 5.3 - Report on recommended methods for improving niche construction and analysing/predicting network dynamics

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1 Version History

Version	Authors	Summary of changes	Date
0.1	F. Jordán	Initial draft	28.08.202 4
0.2	F. Jordán, A. Hidas	Final version	06.09.202 4
1.0	Claudio de Majo, Daniele Iudicone, Stephane Peasant	Final proofreading and submission	24.10.202 4

2 Executive summary

Deliverable D5.3 is the output of Task T5.3 (mostly T5.3.2). The aim is to provide analyses that support niche modelling and the development of indicators for D5.5. This deliverable is based on algorithms and network data presented in D5.1 and D5.2. Here, we use smaller, aggregated versions of those networks, and study them using old and new tools for network analysis. Deliverable D5.3 focuses on differential equation-based simulations, while dynamical analyses such as “*in silico* node removal experiments” are still in progress.

The Global Planktonic Interactome (GPI) network was aggregated by the Eigen algorithm and several versions of the aggregated network (at different threshold levels) were studied by measures of centrality (TI), asymmetry (AG), redundancy (TO), functional diversity (IPD) and similarity (REGE). First, we outline the methods, present the results and discuss their relevance for niche construction. Finally, we discuss the ecological role and potential importance of the identified key organisms.

This document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

3 Introduction

Ecology is about the co-existence of the diversity of species. Microorganisms have been massively understudied for decades but recent methods and algorithms make it possible to understand better also their coexistence in multi-species contexts. While in classical food web research, the microbial world was represented by a single or a few trophic groups (e.g. "bacteria", "phytoplankton", "zooplankton"), recent studies explicitly address the question of how to dramatically increase the resolution of the microbial trophic system (see D'Alelio et al. 2016). This makes it possible to answer questions that are routinely asked for higher organisms also for microbes: which ones are generalists or specialists, which pairs have overlapping trophic niches, which ones are highly connected to others. All the ecological knowledge we have for fish and mammals might be studied also for microbes (e.g. candidate keystone species in key network positions, Jordán 2009).

It is also clear that prokaryotes, but also protists or the larvae of eukaryotes, have partly similar but partly different ecological processes of relevance. For example, instead of classical predator-prey relationships, they are connected very frequently by metabolic interactions (e.g. Giordano et al. 2024). This is not substantially different but needs different methods to reveal. Also, while for higher organisms we have tons of information on pairwise interactions (e.g. predator and prey, host and parasite), this is hard to get for microorganisms (mostly because of the huge number of species or strains). For this reason, instead of well-documented lists of ecological, inter-specific interactions, we have statistical data on positive or negative associations (i.e. co-occurrence). Co-occurrence can be caused by multiple mechanisms and it is still unclear which are the combinations of positive and negative effects that result in positive and negative co-occurrences. In particular, negative co-occurrences are often hard to clearly understand (Taketani et al. 2018), resulting potentially from exploitative competition (Barberán et al. 2012, Ma et al. 2020, Wu et al. 2021, Gao et al. 2022), interference competition (Berry and Widder 2014), predation (Mikhailov et al. 2019, Lee et al. 2022), parasitism (Siles et al. 2021, Varsadiya et al. 2021), amensalism (Yang et al. 2021, Codello et al. 2023) or just different habitat preference (Morueta-Holme et al. 2016).

A strong mutualism clearly leads to positive co-occurrence but the situation is more complicated for both competition and predation. In the case of competition, positive association (coexistence) is generally needed for a competitive relationship but if it becomes very strong, it can lead to negative association (i.e. exclusion). This means that the strength of the interaction determines its sign. In the case of predation, if the predator is successful, we see a positive association (i.e. predation), while if the prey is an advantage, we can see a negative association (i.e. predator avoidance).

Still, it is a major challenge and also an excellent opportunity to use co-occurrence data to better understand multi-species ecosystems and to better map the multi-dimensional niche space. The latest data and results describe spatial variability of co-occurrences at the global level (Gaudin et al. 2024) and the vulnerability of the interactome network (Chaffron et al. 2021). For biological interpretation and functional understanding, complex networks can be transformed into aggregated networks of larger components. For the smaller networks, an arsenal of network analytical tools can be used and key ecological patterns and processes can be quantified. This is our aim in this report.

4 Results

4.1 The GPI network

Deliverable D5.1 provided a reference catalogue for network construction algorithms (Budnich et al. 2022) and deliverable D5.2 presented the Global Planktonic Interactome network (GPI, Chaffron et al. 2023). In our task T5.3 (*Analyse network structures and their dynamics*) we used these data.

The nodes of the GPI network are organisms (sequences) defined by their lineages, with additional information on the marine biome and the ocean region. For example, the data field

Eukaryota|Opisthokonta|Holomycota|Fungi|Ascomycota|Saccharomycotina|Saccharomycetales|Saccharomycodes|Saccharomycodes+ludwigii

Coastal_Polar_Trades_Westerlies

[AO]_[IO]_[MS]_[NAO]_[NPO]_[RS]_[SAO]_[SO]_[SPO]

provides information on the organism (in red), the marine biome (in blue) and the ocean region (in green). Additionally, the network represents statistically determined associations (co-occurrence) among the organisms (see D5.2).

In order to take a comparative approach and assess spatial variability, we constructed four ocean region-specific subnetworks for the positive associations in the GPI network (AO, SO, IO, PO). The number of nodes for these "positive subnetworks" were $N_{AO} = 10476$, $N_{SO} = 9598$, $N_{PO} = 9782$, $N_{IO} = 8045$ (after deleting the isolated nodes). The most central organisms of the positive co-occurrence networks for the 4 ocean regions are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. (a): The 10 most central organisms in the 4 ocean region-specific subnetworks of positive co-occurrences. Colours show some selected, consistently central organisms, see Table 1b.

AO		PO		IO		SO	
	TI		TI		TI		TI
b659ab07521880f21415cee8d765227	3,34E-04	01814330bd443b102bdf64153a48e25	3,43E-04	b659ab07521880f21415cee8d765227	4,39E-04	b659ab07521880f21415cee8d765227	3,34E-04
01814330bd443b102bdf64153a48e25	3,21E-04	105c1450c09d4080da86431514444f9	3,35E-04	105c1450c09d4080da86431514444f9	4,11E-04	c7b839fe1561bc4cc0cd425a84ea31f	3,30E-04
a186923d14926c780028e27b9311ef	3,11E-04	ba0b0b08c853c401a5ec0e9b0b43a4	3,31E-04	6a5142141b4b440e16a33d799c9e0a	4,09E-04	105c1450c09d4080da86431514444f9	3,15E-04
c7b839fe1561bc4cc0cd425a84ea31f	2,90E-04	c7b839fe1561bc4cc0cd425a84ea31f	3,28E-04	9ed0cc1d36a702be22b2888c791976	4,08E-04	12ef08d3b38386739178b023ee3a364	3,13E-04
ba0b0b08c853c401a5ec0e9b0b43a4	2,90E-04	b659ab07521880f21415cee8d765227	3,28E-04	aa8d03c670f35d2efb9ca3a7349159	3,78E-04	ba0b0b08c853c401a5ec0e9b0b43a4	3,09E-04
105c1450c09d4080da86431514444f9	2,89E-04	a186923d14926c780028e27b9311ef	3,16E-04	8088af1e7301b0c48f93a070e464173	3,73E-04	b84d4401f6d70e70f9a6a69e750cca	3,02E-04
ee0c7c1ef2919a48d1f76168866df	2,85E-04	12ef08d3b38386739178b023ee3a364	3,09E-04	d53846e4e52b5c1f592ed30c34868	3,70E-04	0f19412b8e1d58e0f9c39c319c64	3,00E-04
70a81bcb6ca4c4865c2f6477173028	2,84E-04	158b30f06311e913c559a1c78505a71	3,07E-04	43ac4ed11ae67abcb7d07c01a6c5f9da	3,69E-04	aa8d03c670f35d2efb9ca3a7349159	3,00E-04
9ef0f3ec43085b5a91917bf789a34d	2,83E-04	aa8d03c670f35d2efb9ca3a7349159	3,01E-04	2317724dfc317403907d7ff6f78b4c	3,63E-04	95146e5e2d43a5454da14143c7f5aad1	2,98E-04
2a994ae8057231d2e99c62ff0c4e831e	2,79E-04	3c43c3aac0f6d53bab509f5c844ec40	2,99E-04	046cc0b64148f59c160b74b613717879	3,61E-04	6a5142141b4b440e16a33d799c9e0a	2,97E-04

Organism	Biome	Ocean Region
75b7ed484b70045596e0bd2471143d7	Eukaryota	Coastal_Polar_Trades_Westerlies
25439cac544bd224b04ae7bc7b2e58	Eukaryota Excavata Discoba Euglenozoa Diplomonadida Rhynchopis Rhynchopus+sp	Coastal_Polar_Trades_Westerlies
2a994ae8057231d2e99c62ff0c4e831e	Eukaryota Harosaj Rhizaria Retaria Polycestinea Colodaria Collophoridae Disolenia Disolenia+zanguebarica	Coastal_Polar_Trades_Westerlies
105c1450c09d4080da86431514444f9	Eukaryota Harosaj Rhizaria Retaria Polycestinea Colodaria Thalassicolidae Thalassicollia Thalassicollia+nucleata	Coastal_Polar_Trades_Westerlies
9011fc50706d600c4b371911b225	Eukaryota Opisthokonta Holozoa Metazoa environmental samples uncultured metazoan	Coastal_Polar_Trades_Westerlies
b659ab07521880f21415cee8d765227	Eukaryota Opisthokonta Holomycota Fungi Ascomycota Saccharomycotina Saccharomycetales Saccharomycodes+ludwigii	Coastal_Polar_Trades_Westerlies
ba0b0b08c853c401a5ec0e9b0b43a4	Eukaryota Harosaj Rhizaria Retaria Polycestinea Colodaria Sphaerocoides Rhaphidizoum Rhaphidizoum+maculiferum	Coastal_Polar_Trades_Westerlies
c7b839fe1561bc4cc0cd425a84ea31f	Eukaryota Harosaj Stramenopiles Ochrophyta Chrysochyceae Chrysochloride Paraphysomonas Paraphysomonas+sp	Coastal_Polar_Trades_Westerlies
01814330bd443b102bdf64153a48e25	Eukaryota Harosaj Rhizaria Retaria Polycestinea Nassellaria Nassellaria_X Nassellaria_X+sp	Coastal_Polar_Trades_Westerlies
a186923d14926c780028e27b9311ef	Eukaryota Archaeplastida Viridiplantae Chlorophyta Pyrammonadales Halosphaera Halosphaera+sp	Coastal_Polar_Trades_Westerlies

Based on these ranks, we can see that a diversity of organisms may be in highly central positions in the biome-specific networks but *Saccharomycodes ludwigii* (azure) and *Thalassicollia nucleata* (green) seem to be consistently central in the global ocean. An indicator organism for the Atlantic Ocean is, based only on the top 10 most central ones shown in Table 1a, *Disolenia zanguebarica* (red).

One can also see that some organisms are not fully determined ("Eukaryota" in blue). We note here that several cliques describe various versions of the same organism (e.g. there is a 5-clique composed of 5 different versions of *Pseudocalanus moutoni*). In a better case, another 5-clique is composed of 5 different dinoflagellate species and this is biologically perfectly plausible.

These are different sequence fragments annotated to the same species but treated separately. These latter notes support the need for studying also aggregated networks that are less noisy and biologically more meaningful.

On other datasets, we tested the spatial variability of co-occurrence networks, along horizontal (offshore) and vertical (depth) gradients (Castillo et al., in preparation). Several network-level (global) properties of co-occurrence networks showed correlations with gradients and also with the concentrations of certain molecules in seawater (e.g. nitrate).

Co-occurrence (statistical positive or negative association) is an overall output of several mechanisms. In order to better understand niche dimensions (both biotic, e.g. trophic, and abiotic, i.e. chemistry) we needed to better understand the potential mechanisms generating co-occurrences. Decomposing co-occurrence into various sources of generative mechanisms is quite challenging but we made a couple of steps towards this direction.

Thus, we were interested in a potential mechanism generating co-occurrence. We hypothesised that a positive co-occurrence can be generated as the outcome of a pair of negative co-occurrences (following the "enemy of enemy is a friend" principle). This hypothesis was based on preliminary results showing that the networks of negative co-occurrences contained absolutely no 3-loops, according to the expectations. Signed transitivity would suggest a positive relationship between two negative neighbours. This kind of transitivity works in several kinds of networks (e.g. social networks) but we are not aware of any application for signed co-occurrence networks. We used two versions of the topological importance (TIⁿ) index: TI² for the network of negative associations and TI¹ for the network of positive associations. If a chain of two negative associations (from A to B and from B to C) results in a positive A-C association, in a transitive way, we can expect a large overlap between strong indirect A-C effects in the negative network and strong direct A-C effects in the positive network. In the four subnetworks for the biomes, only around 1% of the 2-step negative indirect effects were paralleled with strong direct positive co-occurrences (AO: 44/4354 = 0.0101, SO: 24/3412 = 0.007, PO: 22/2236 = 0.0098 and IO: 11/1322 = 0.008). This suggests that the transitivity of negative associations consistently does NOT generate direct positive associations.

Another potential mechanism generating positive co-occurrences is a strong external (abiotic, non-living) factor (e.g. iron, salinity, temperature) that is preferred by several organisms. In this case we can expect cliques or high clustering, as all organisms preferring the external factor become associated also with each other. We checked n-cliques for the GPI network.

The original, large GPI network provides a nice overview on the complexity of the marine plankton but its functional and biological relevance are limited.

We explored several approaches to network aggregation (e.g. Jaccard, REGE), also by filtering out weak associations (using thresholds), but finally, only one algorithm was successful (see below). The others created highly fragmented networks (with up to 583 fragments), long linear chains (see Figure 1) or did not run properly.

Figure 1. The GPI network (for the positive co-occurrences) after filtering for weight (at threshold of 0.5, $N = 3195$) and aggregated by the Jaccard method (to $N = 905$ nodes). Note the linear structures considered as aggregation artefacts.

4.2 Network aggregation

Since network position (to some extent) determines functioning, nodes in similar positions are expected to be functionally similar. One way to reduce network complexity is to aggregate nodes of identical (or similar) topological positions into larger functional groups. Studying functional groups provide a simplified but more understandable and often less noisy (e.g. while its constituent species may have diverse phenology and seasonal dynamics, the functional group may remain more or less the same) representation of the studied ecosystem. This has a long history in food web research (Hirata and Ulanowicz 1985, Yodzis and Winemiller 1999, Luczkovich et al. 2003, Gauzens et al. 2013) but the approach is relatively new for both microbial communities and co-occurrence networks. Aggregation may be based on mathematical algorithms (see the examples above) and biological experience and intuition (Jordán et al. 2018). Ideally, these provide the same results. Since the properties of aggregated networks are different (Martinez 1991, Hall and Raffaelli 1991), it

is crucial (but still understudied) to understand the systematic effects of various clustering (Yodzis and Winemiller 1999) and, in general, aggregation methods (see Giacomuzzo and Jordán 2021). It is important to note that positional similarities in networks quantify and characterise trophic similarities and trophic niches.

We could not successfully use several aggregation algorithms. The original GPI network was too large and also its topological properties are different from the ones of food webs most aggregation algorithms have been developed and optimised to.

Finally, we could use the results of the leading eigenvector algorithm provided by the Partner CNRS (see also Newman 2006). We used the "eigen twice community" attribute of the GPI dataset to aggregate. This provided 90 aggregates (components with >1 original graph node), while several original graph nodes remained un-aggregated. In a sense, these can be considered of key importance (following the definition of keystone species as single-species functional groups, Bond 1994).

The size of the aggregated components (C) ranged from 4 (in C89) to 270 (in C4). In particular, C2 contained 212 organisms.

For one example, the original graph node id

`b659ab07521880ff21415cee8d765227`

coded organism with lineage description

`Eukaryota|Opisthokonta|Holomycota|Fungi|Ascomycota|Saccharomycotina|Saccharomycetales|Saccharomycodes|Saccharomycodes+ludwigii`

and additional information on spatial annotations (biomes and ocean zones)

`Coastal_Polar_Trades_Westerlies`

`[AO]_[IO]_[MS]_[NAO]_[NPO]_[RS]_[SAO]_[SO]_[SPO]`

We have 4 different graph nodes with the same lineage description (with differences only in the latter spatial annotations). These four are coded as 5569, 10017, 13705 and 18140. Each of them aggregated into the same component (C2), reflecting their similarity in co-occurring partners.

We constructed three networks with different t thresholds. With $t=0.1$, the number of nodes is $N=50$ (Figure 2a), with $t=0.5$ $N=22$ (Figure 2b) and with $t=0.9$ $N=17$ (Figure 2c). In each of these binary networks there was a single giant **component** and each other node was a single isolate. In the following analyses, we only study the giant component (also for the number of nodes N).

In the GPI network, the full database contained $N = 20810$ organisms (sequences). During the aggregation algorithm, most of these (20801) were aggregated into 90 mathematically defined components (functional groups), but 9 of the original organisms (sequences) remained un-aggregated with anything else. These are 7067 (Neoceratium), 6726 (Holodynophyta), 8335 (Chloromonas), 1547 (Holodynophyta), 9513 (Holodynophyta), 9754 (Retaria), 11866 (Pelagophyceae), 19998 (Alphaproteobacteria) and 336 (Cyclopoida; see the precise lineages given in Table 2). These organisms are "single-species functional groups", according to our aggregation algorithm, so can be considered keystone species (sensu Bond 1994).

Beyond these 9 un-aggregated organisms, the aggregated networks also contain large, aggregated components. In the network with $t=0.9$, there are 8 (17-9) components: C11 (containing 11 organisms), C28 (17), C31 (2), C49 (231), C56 (31), C58 (100), C70 (2) and C72 (2; Table 3 shows the organisms in two small components C31 and C70).

Table 2. The 8 un-aggregated components of the network with $t = 0.5$.

7067;"Eukaryota|Harosa|Alveolata|Myzozoa|Holodinophyta|Dinophyceae|Gonyaulacales|Ceratiaceae|Neoceratium|Neoceratium+tenuis"
 6726;"Eukaryota|Harosa|Alveolata|Myzozoa|Holodinophyta|Malv_II|Malv_II_clade_10-11|Malv_II_clade_10-11_X|Malv_II_clade_10-11_X+sp."
 8335;"Eukaryota|Archaeplastida|Viridiplantae|Chlorophyta|Chlorophyceae|Chlamydomonadales|environmental samples|uncultured Chloromonas"
 1547;"Eukaryota|Harosa|Alveolata|Myzozoa|Holodinophyta|Malv_I|Malv_I_clade_4|Malv_I_clade_4_X|Malv_I_clade_4_X+sp."
 9513;"Eukaryota|Harosa|Alveolata|Myzozoa|Holodinophyta|Dinophyceae"
 9754;"Eukaryota|Harosa|Rhizaria|Retaria|clade_RadA|clade_RadA_X|clade_RadA_X+sp."
 11866;"Eukaryota|Harosa|Stramenopiles|Ochrophyta|Pelagophyceae|MMETSP|MMETSP+RCC1024"
 19998;"Bacteria;Proteobacteria;Alphaproteobacteria;SAR11 clade;Surface 1;uncultured bacterium;"
 336;"Eukaryota|Opisthokonta|Holozoa|Metazoa|Arthropoda|Crustacea|Maxillopoda|Copepoda|Cyclopoida|Cyclopoida_X|Cyclopoida_X+sp."

Table 3. The composition of components C31 and C70.

C31: 4821;"Eukaryota|Harosa|Rhizaria|Retaria|Polycystinea|Nassellaria|Nassellaria_X|Nassellaria_X+sp."
 7564;"Eukaryota|Harosa|Alveolata|Myzozoa|Holodinophyta|Malv_V|Malv_V_X|Malv_V_X+sp."
 C70: 1369;"Eukaryota|Harosa|Rhizaria|Retaria|Polycystinea|Collodaria|Sphaerozoidae|Sphaerozoum|Sphaerozoum+punctatum"
 7871;"Eukaryota|Harosa|Rhizaria|Retaria|Polycystinea|Collodaria|Sphaerozoidae"

a

b

c

Figure 2. The aggregated network with $t=0.5$ (a). We also show networks with $t=0.1$ (b) and $t=0.9$ (c).

Table 4. The TI-based centrality ranks for the aggregated networks with $t = 0.1$, $t = 0.5$ and $t = 0.9$.

t= 0,1		t= 0,5		t= 0,9	
node ID	TI	node ID	TI	node ID	TI
9513	0,166	9513	0,183	9513	0,204
7067	0,111	7067	0,132	7067	0,110
6726	0,108	6726	0,111	6726	0,098
11866	0,103	C70	0,079	11866	0,097
C31	0,051	9754	0,059	8335	0,080
C70	0,044	C31	0,055	C31	0,064
9754	0,033	8335	0,053	C70	0,058
C72	0,027	11866	0,051	336	0,056
C28	0,027	C72	0,036	9754	0,056
8335	0,019	336	0,035	C28	0,051
C11	0,018	C11	0,035	C72	0,030
336	0,018	C28	0,035	1547	0,025
C24	0,015	C24	0,027	19998	0,016
C49	0,013	C89	0,018	C49	0,014
C56	0,013	19998	0,018	C56	0,014
C58	0,013	1547	0,018	C58	0,014
C0	0,012	C17	0,009	C11	0,013
C3	0,012	C19	0,009		
C17	0,012	C49	0,009		
C19	0,012	C56	0,009		
C12	0,009	C58	0,009		
C14	0,009	C0	0,009		
C18	0,009				
C6	0,008				
C25	0,008				
C40	0,008				
C75	0,008				
C61	0,008				
C65	0,008				
19998	0,008				
C55	0,008				
C88	0,008				
C89	0,007				
C78	0,007				
C1	0,006				
1547	0,006				
C32	0,004				
C68	0,004				
C74	0,004				
C87	0,004				
C41	0,004				
C44	0,004				
C46	0,004				
C50	0,004				
C51	0,004				
C57	0,004				
C81	0,004				
C2	0,003				
C7	0,003				
C23	0,003				

4.3 Network analysis

Table 4 shows the centrality rank of nodes, according to the Tl^3 -index, for the networks with $t = 0.1$, $t = 0.5$ and $t = 0.9$ (see also the Annex; calculations made by the CosbiLab Graph software, Valentini and Jordán 2010).

The three most central organisms are 9513 (Holodynophyta), 7067 (Neoceratium, a dinoflagellate) and 6726 (Holodynophyta). This shows the dominance of these organisms in terms of co-occurrence: they are unaggregated, non-redundant, but link diverse large aggregated groups to each other. This suggests a crucial positional importance in the marine microbial system. The other central organisms in the GPI network have been aggregated into less central components.

The most central groups can be compared between the original GPI subnetworks (Table 1) and the aggregated networks (Table 4). Considering the aggregated network with $t = 0.5$, the overlap is surprisingly small, with only 2 organisms being part of the top of both centrality ranks (e.g. *Rhaphidozoum acuferum* in yellow is part of C49 and *Paraphysomonas* in brown, a Chrysophyta, is part of C58).

Interaction asymmetry and causality

Following an old interest in the asymmetry of interactions in ecological networks (e.g. Koch et al. 2024), we determined the most asymmetric relationships, based on the Tl^3 -index. This approach was explored earlier (Jordán et al. 2014) and it is recently being developed and tested for novel datasets (Jordán et al. 2024a, 2024b, Hidas et al., in preparation). The key aim is to identify critically important causal links while massively reducing complexity. For the network with $t = 0.5$, we determined maximal structural asymmetry ($A_{max} = 0.43$), derived the threshold for causal interactions ($c = 2/3 * A_{max} = 0.28$), and the number of links in the asymmetry graph ($N_{AC} = 9$, $L_{AC} = 6$). The identity of organisms in the asymmetry graphs is shown in Figure 3.

Trophic overlap and interaction diversity

Based on strong and weak relationships determined by the Tl^3 -index, the approach of trophic overlap (Jordán et al. 2009) was developed to quantify the uniqueness vs redundancy of interaction structures in food webs. Species with typically non-overlapping neighbourhoods of strong interactors are considered more unique with a less redundant food web position. Since the TO-index is threshold-dependent, a general index was developed for characterising the overall functional diversity in a trophic network. We used the Interaction Profile Diversity (IPD, Lin et al. 2022) value for assessing the functional diversity of the aggregated network with $t = 0.5$ (main diagonal removed). Its value was quite high ($IPD_{0.5} = 0.717925$) compared to a large set of 92 trophic networks (Lin et al. 2022), suggesting a network architecture of low compactness and a low level of redundancy.

Figure 3. The asymmetry graphs for networks with $t = 0.5$ (a), $t = 0.1$ (b) and $t = 0.9$ (c).

Regular equivalence and similarity

We used an optimised version of the regular equivalence (REGE) algorithm (Batagelj et al. 1992, Borgatti and Everett 1993). This uses regular block modelling with 2 blocks, based on the tabu search algorithm (no diagonal considered, 30 iterations, 25 penalty iterations). Calculations were performed by the UCINET software (Borgatti et al. 2002). For the network with $t = 0.5$, graph nodes were assigned to the 2 blocks as:

block 1 (14 nodes): [C0 C11 C17 C19 C24 8335 C28 1547 C49 C56 C58 C72 19998 C89]

block 2 (8 nodes): [7067 6726 C31 9513 9754 11866 C70 336]

Threshold-sensitivity

Results may be sensitive to the $t = 0.5$ threshold parameter, so we performed all calculations for $t = 0.1$ and $t = 0.9$.

While the number of nodes is different from $N_{0.5} = 22$ ($N_{0.1} = 50$ and $N_{0.9} = 17$), the top 3 nodes in the Tl^3 rank are the same (in the same order) for networks with $t = 0.1$ and $t = 0.9$.

The size of the asymmetry graphs was somewhat changing for the networks with $t = 0.1$ ($A_{max} = 0.46$, $c = 0.3$, $N_{AG} = 18$, $L_{AG} = 13$) and with $t = 0.9$ ($A_{max} = 0.44$, $c = 0.29$, $N_{AG} = 8$, $L_{AG} = 5$).

The IPD-values were also quite consistent ($IPD_{0.1} = 0.715861$ and $IPD_{0.9} = 0.706308$).

In block modelling, one of the 2 blocks of the $t = 0.1$ network is compared to a single node (component C0). In the $t = 0.9$ network, the 2 blocks contained 8 and 9 nodes.

4.4 Limitations and future extensions

Data quality still needs to be improved, both in terms of creating weighted co-occurrence networks (instead of binary ones) and better defining the identity of sequences (e.g. 145;"Eukaryota"). Also, we need to consider weighted associations in co-occurrence networks.

Comparative analyses (for biomes and regions) seem to be highly useful to better address functionality. We will extend our preliminary analysis on comparing co-occurrence networks for different biomes (e.g. AO vs SO), studying spatially and temporally defined subsystems below the biome-level and compare networks representing different association signs (i.e. negative vs positive). We need to better understand how to compare positive and negative associations (their mechanistic causes and consequences). Generally speaking, understanding trophic and non-trophic (e.g. habitat, space) dimensions of niche modelling needs a better decomposition of co-existence into various niche dimensions.

Small, aggregated networks have several advantages (see above). One of them is the possibility of dynamical analyses (i.e. simulations). As soon as the topology of the aggregated networks (especially with $t=0.9$) is better understood from a microbiological point of view, we will try to get dynamical parameters and construct simulation models (e.g. differential equations). If this is hopeless (this is a risk factor), the mitigation plan is to perform vulnerability analysis by in silico node removal experiments (see Dunne et al. 2002).

Specifically, we intend to perform a comparative analysis of causality Indices, including the one used above and alternatives (Taruttis et al. 2015) used already for marine plankton (Causal Network Analysis, Amaral-Zettler et al. 2021). The general interest in asymmetric relationships is growing (Koch et al. 2024) and might lead to key information on critically important interactions and special roles particular organisms play in community control.

Statistical co-occurrences (positive and negative associations) are the outcome of several mechanisms. This means that essentially all dimensions of the niche space influence co-existence and co-occurrence. There is still a long way to go and a major challenge to precisely understand the relative importance of various mechanisms (and niche dimensions) in shaping associations and co-occurrences. As we have shown earlier, various mechanisms may leave different fingerprints in the co-occurrence network. We will need to clarify this issue.

We also need to better understand the biological properties of aggregated groups and we may explore additional aggregation algorithms.

As the biggest challenge, we need to develop dynamical simulation models for these systems (based on differential equations, network rewiring or node/link removal, in this decreasing order of complexity).

In a parallel project (PredAqua), we test a number of network analysis-based predictions in freshwater mesocosm systems. The results, if generalizable, may feed back to this research (e.g. considering the most predictive centrality indices). This will also support experimental validation (Task 5.4).

4.5 Feeding other Tasks and WPs

Our results provide a quantitative description of central and peripheral as well as unique and redundant nodes. Also, asymmetrical interactions of causality and mathematically defined aggregates of nodes based on network similarity. All these methods contribute to reducing complexity, improving functional understanding and hopefully supporting strategic thinking and management from a systems perspective. Indicator development may capitalise on these outputs (see D5.5).

5 Conclusions

Our purpose was to close the loop from sampling biological organisms to their omics-based description, to bioinformatics analysis, to systems ecology models and back to biological information, as much as possible. Identifying key organisms and functional groups, as well as crucial interactions among them, is a way to manage complexity and put biological knowledge into a more holistic context.

Based on the data we got and the modelling approach we have taken, we can see that some dinophytes and dinoflagellates are quite unique (9513, 7067, not being aggregated with others) and also central (having several associated partners) in the marine planktonic ecosystem. These groups are known for having multiple relationships with other organisms, playing important roles in the trophic system and being capable of switching among energy pathways (mixotrophy). These properties make them of extreme potential importance for mitigating human impact and supporting the adaptability of the oceanic ecosystem to environmental stressors (Mitra 2024).

The SAR11 clade of Alphaproteobacteria (19998) is among the most abundant groups of heterotrophic bacteria in the ocean, playing a vital role in the global carbon cycle by recycling dissolved organic carbon (DOC). They are key players in the microbial loop, where they process organic matter that other organisms cannot, making nutrients available to other microorganisms, especially in oligotrophic (nutrient-poor) environments.

Among the key groups, we also see Chlorophytes and other photosynthetic Eukaryotes (uncultured Chlorophyta: 1547, uncultured Chloromonas: 8335, Pelagophyceae: 11866). These algae are primary producers. They are foundational to marine food webs, supporting higher trophic levels. Members of Pelagophyceae are known for their involvement in forming picoplankton communities and are crucial in nutrient-poor environments. Chlorophytes interact with a variety of marine organisms, providing a food source for herbivorous zooplankton. They also play a role in biogeochemical cycles, particularly in carbon and oxygen dynamics.

A key species at higher trophic level is a cyclopoid copepod (336), linking primary producers and higher trophic levels, serving as prey for fish and other marine animals. Their grazing on phytoplankton can influence algal blooms, and their role as prey supports commercially important fish populations.

Finally, one of the Identified key species belongs to Rhizarians (clade RadA: 9754). They are involved in the carbon cycle through the sequestration of carbon in their silica shells, which, after sinking (marine snow), contributes to the ocean's biological pump and is a limiting nutrient for certain types of phytoplankton, such as diatoms. Clade RadA is part of the Radiolaria, often forming symbiotic relationships with algae (dinoflagellates or cyanobacteria).

Also, we can see that these organisms have highly asymmetric, causal interactions with large aggregates (functional groups) of diverse organisms, further increasing their trophic roles and importance. For example, the Holodinophyta coded as 6726 (Malv_II_clade_10-11_X+sp.) is strongly influencing the aggregate C0 composed of 98 organisms, including the radiozoa *Eucyrtidium hexastichum* (229), *Gymnodinium* sp. strain7 (401) or the collodaria *Thalassicolla nucleata* (516).

This massive simplification of the co-occurrence network into a few key nodes and links surely results in unrealistic results and the loss of information (see Patten 1975 for a classical example) but, at the same time, serves for potentially useful and applicable indicators (as numerical indices) identifying indicator species within a systemic context (opposed to classical single-species indicators that are associated with a habitat or an environmental factor).

The detailed analysis and discussion of all the 20801 organisms is not possible but the approach and the pipeline presented are being further used for exploring biologically relevant information for further interpretation.

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7 Annexes

Annex 1. a: the matrix of indirect effects among nodes in up to 3 steps (TI^3). b: the topological overlap (TO) values with threshold $t=0.01$. c: the centrality rank of nodes according to TI^3 . d: the redundancy rank of nodes according to $TO^3_{0.01}$. All data for the network with $t = 0.5$.

a

103	C0	7067	C11	C17	C19	6726	C24	8335	C28	1547	C31	C49	9513	C56	C58	9754	11866	C70	C72	19998	306	C89
C0	0.03	0.01	0.01	0	0	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0	0.01	0	0	0.01	0	0	0	0	0	0
7067	0.09	0.14	0.17	0.45	0.45	0.13	0.2	0.13	0.17	0.27	0.15	0.05	0.08	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.08	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.03
C11	0.04	0.06	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.07	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.04	0.09	0.03	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0	0.02	0.02
C17	0	0.04	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
C19	0	0.04	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6726	0.43	0.12	0.17	0.08	0.08	0.12	0.19	0.12	0.17	0.25	0.14	0.05	0.08	0.05	0.05	0.1	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.06
C24	0.04	0.05	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0	0.01	0.02
8335	0.04	0.07	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.07	0.04	0.06	0.05	0.04	0.1	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.08	0.03	0.04	0.12	0.03
C28	0.04	0.06	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.07	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.04	0.09	0.03	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0	0.02	0.02
1547	0.04	0.06	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.02	0	0.01	0	0	0.01	0	0.01	0	0	0	0
C31	0.06	0.08	0.14	0.06	0.06	0.09	0.05	0.1	0.14	0.06	0.07	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.03
C49	0	0	0.01	0	0	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.01	0	0.01	0.01	0	0.01	0.01
9513	0.08	0.12	0.18	0.07	0.07	0.13	0.2	0.15	0.18	0.08	0.16	0.46	0.15	0.46	0.46	0.16	0.09	0.13	0.18	0.07	0.17	0.28
C56	0	0	0.01	0	0	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.01	0	0.01	0.01	0	0.01	0.01
C58	0	0	0.01	0	0	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.01	0	0.01	0.01	0	0.01	0.01
9754	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.09	0.13	0.1	0.15	0.08	0.05	0.22
11866	0.01	0.01	0.01	0	0	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.01	0	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.11	0.11	0.12	0.15	0.25	0.14	0.05
C70	0.02	0.06	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.11	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.07	0.04	0.04	0.13	0.19	0.1	0.17	0.27	0.17	0.06
C72	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.1	0.12	0.08	0.06	0.07	0.05	0.05	0.05
19998	0	0.01	0	0	0	0	0.01	0	0	0	0	0	0.01	0	0	0.03	0.1	0.07	0.04	0.06	0.03	0.01
306	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.08	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.11	0.08	0.05	0.07	0.06	0.03
C89	0.01	0.01	0.01	0	0	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0	0.01	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.07	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.04

b

103	C0	7067	C11	C17	C19	6726	C24	8335	C28	1547	C31	C49	9513	C56	C58	9754	11866	C70	C72	19998	306	C89
C0	0	0.16	0.16	0.09	0.09	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0	0.16	0	0	0.16	0.02	0.16	0.11	0	0.11	0.05
7067	0.16	0	0.45	0.16	0.16	0.5	0.45	0.5	0.45	0.27	0.45	0.11	0.5	0.11	0.11	0.45	0.32	0.5	0.41	0.18	0.45	0.3
C11	0.16	0.45	0	0.16	0.16	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.27	0.45	0.11	0.45	0.11	0.11	0.41	0.27	0.45	0.36	0.14	0.41	0.25
C17	0.09	0.16	0.16	0	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0	0.16	0	0	0.11	0.02	0.16	0.09	0	0.14	0.02
C19	0.09	0.16	0.16	0.16	0	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0	0.16	0	0	0.11	0.02	0.16	0.09	0	0.14	0.02
6726	0.16	0.5	0.45	0.16	0.16	0	0.45	0.5	0.45	0.27	0.45	0.11	0.5	0.11	0.11	0.45	0.32	0.5	0.41	0.18	0.45	0.3
C24	0.16	0.45	0.45	0.16	0.16	0.45	0	0.45	0.45	0.27	0.45	0.11	0.45	0.11	0.11	0.41	0.27	0.45	0.36	0.14	0.41	0.25
8335	0.16	0.5	0.45	0.16	0.16	0.5	0.45	0	0.45	0.27	0.45	0.11	0.5	0.11	0.11	0.45	0.32	0.5	0.41	0.18	0.45	0.3
C28	0.16	0.45	0.45	0.16	0.16	0.45	0.45	0.45	0	0.27	0.45	0.11	0.45	0.11	0.11	0.41	0.27	0.45	0.36	0.14	0.41	0.25
1547	0.16	0.27	0.27	0.16	0.16	0.27	0.27	0.27	0	0.27	0.02	0.27	0.02	0.02	0.23	0.09	0.27	0.18	0.02	0.23	0.07	0.07
C31	0.16	0.45	0.45	0.16	0.16	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.27	0	0.11	0.45	0.11	0.11	0.41	0.27	0.45	0.36	0.14	0.41	0.25
C49	0	0.11	0.11	0	0	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.02	0.11	0	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.02	0.11	0.11
9513	0.16	0.5	0.45	0.16	0.16	0.5	0.45	0.5	0.45	0.27	0.45	0.11	0	0.11	0.11	0.45	0.32	0.5	0.41	0.18	0.45	0.3
C56	0	0.11	0.11	0	0	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.02	0.11	0.11	0.11	0	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.02	0.11	0.11
C58	0	0.11	0.11	0	0	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.02	0.11	0.11	0.11	0	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.02	0.11	0.11
9754	0.16	0.45	0.41	0.11	0.11	0.45	0.41	0.45	0.41	0.23	0.41	0.11	0.45	0.11	0.11	0	0.32	0.45	0.41	0.18	0.41	0.3
11866	0.02	0.32	0.27	0.02	0.02	0.32	0.27	0.32	0.27	0.11	0.09	0.27	0.11	0.32	0.11	0.11	0.32	0	0.32	0.18	0.32	0.27
C70	0.16	0.5	0.45	0.16	0.16	0.5	0.45	0.5	0.45	0.27	0.45	0.11	0.5	0.11	0.11	0.45	0.32	0	0.41	0.18	0.45	0.3
C72	0.11	0.41	0.36	0.09	0.09	0.41	0.36	0.41	0.36	0.18	0.36	0.11	0.41	0.11	0.11	0.41	0.32	0.41	0	0.18	0.41	0.3
19998	0	0.18	0.14	0	0	0.18	0.14	0.18	0.14	0.02	0.14	0.02	0.18	0.02	0.02	0.18	0.18	0.18	0	0.18	0.18	0.16
306	0.11	0.45	0.41	0.14	0.14	0.45	0.41	0.45	0.41	0.23	0.41	0.11	0.45	0.11	0.11	0.41	0.32	0.45	0.41	0.18	0	0.3
C89	0.05	0.3	0.25	0.02	0.02	0.3	0.25	0.3	0.25	0.07	0.25	0.11	0.3	0.11	0.11	0.3	0.27	0.3	0.3	0.16	0.3	0

RANK	T13
9513	4,02
7067	2,91
6726	2,44
C70	1,73
9754	1,31
C31	1,21
8335	1,17
11866	1,12
C72	0,8
C11	0,78
C28	0,78
336	0,78
C24	0,59
19998	0,4
C89	0,4
1547	0,39
C17	0,2
C19	0,2
C49	0,2
C56	0,2
C58	0,2
C0	0,19

c

RANK	TO3/0.01
7067	7,02
6726	7,02
8335	7,02
9513	7,02
C70	7,02
C11	6,57
C24	6,57
C28	6,57
C31	6,57
9754	6,48
336	6,48
C72	5,93
11866	4,59
C89	4,3
1547	3,82
19998	2,43
C0	2,23
C17	2,23
C19	2,23
C49	1,86
C56	1,86
C58	1,86

d